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Grant agreement N. 773139

DELIVERABLE N° 6.4

Title: DRAFT DISSEMINATION AND TRAINING PLAN

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Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health

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Actual submission date	30-10-2018
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Deliverable lead contractor (organization name)	EPPO
Participants (Partners short names)	All partners
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Level of dissemination	Public
Type of Deliverable	Report.

Abstract:

The training and dissemination plan presents the objectives of training and disseminations and the tools provided to ensure that the objectives will be met.

Partners involved: EPPO and all partners

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Introduction

This document describes the dissemination and training plan of VALITEST (Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health) to define the plan of actions and methodologies for the entire project lifetime (three years).

This document is intended to provide guidelines for the communication and training activities of the VALITEST project.

The **communication strategy** fully adopts the Open Science¹ principles with regards to knowledge dissemination.

1. Project summary

The project summary section is intended to be used by partners for their general communication on the project.

1.1. The call

Call identifier H2020-SFS 2016-2017: Sustainable Food Security

Type of funding scheme: Innovation Action

Work programme topic: SFS-13-2017: *Validation of diagnostic tools for animal and crop health* under the H2020-SFS 2016-2017: *Sustainable Food Security – Resilient and resource efficient value chains* call within the *Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bioeconomy societal challenge*

Coordinating person: Géraldine Anthoine, ANSES

Duration in months: 36 (01/05/2018 to 31/04/2021)

Total budget: 3 201 494 €

Requested grant: 2 997 870 €

1.2. Summary of the objectives of the project

Plant pests (bacteria, viruses, fungi, nematodes, arthropods or weeds) are responsible for major crop losses. Early diagnosis and a rapid response are crucial to reduce the risk of entry and spread of such pests and ultimately their impacts. Furthermore, it is recognized that plant pests can be managed most effectively when control measures are implemented at an early stage of infestation. National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) routinely perform pest diagnosis as part of export certification, import inspections, pest surveillance and eradication programs. In 2016, the Commission on Phytosanitary Measures adopted a recommendation on diagnostics recognizing that ‘pest diagnosis is a cross-cutting issue that underpins most International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) activities. In order to take action against a pest, it must be accurately identified. To enable safe trade, pest diagnosis must further be completed quickly and to a high level of confidence’.

Validation is essential to provide information on the performance of the tests that are used in diagnostics. However, most detection and identification tests are currently only validated on an intra-laboratory basis or through limited test performance studies (TPS), and there is a need to further harmonize practices. The VALITEST project [<https://www.valitest.eu/>] aims at improving diagnostics by producing validation data, harmonizing further processes and enlarging/triggering enlargement of the commercial offer for reliable detection and identification tests.

The project will include two rounds of TPS. The first one will include combinations of pest/test/matrix, prioritized based on the expertise of the project's consortium. The second round will include other combinations based on the needs expressed by various stakeholders. Priorities for validation will then be better aligned to their needs and to the market. To maximize the impact of the project, calls of interest will be organized to include in the validation programme, kits of suppliers outside the consortium and allow participation in the TPS of voluntary proficient laboratories. Current harmonized procedures in Plant Health for validation and organization of TPS will be improved by including

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/open-science>

appropriate statistical approaches and by adapting the process for new promising technologies, such as Next Generation Sequencing. Liaison with regional and international standardization bodies will allow wide dissemination of validation data obtained in this project especially by their inclusion in harmonized diagnostic protocols. The outcomes of the project will stimulate, optimize and strengthen the interactions between stakeholders in Plant Health for better diagnostics and lay the foundations for structuring the quality and the commercial offers for plant health diagnostics tools thanks to a dedicated association and a quality charter.

1.3. List of participants:

n°	Organisation name	Stakeholder group	Country
1	Agence Nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail (ANSES)	Research ⁽¹⁾	France
2	Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO)	Research	Italy
3	Eidgenoessisches Department fuer Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung – Agroscope (WBF)	Research	Switzerland
4	Bioreba AG (BIOREBA)	SME ⁽²⁾	Switzerland
5	Loewe Biochemica GmbH (LOEWE)	SME	Germany
6	European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO)	Policy ⁽³⁾	France
7	Fera Science Ltd. (FERA)	Research	United Kingdom
8	National Institute of Biology (NIB)	Research	Slovenia
9	Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech – Université de Liège (ULG)	Research	Belgium
10	Nederlandse Voedsel en Waren Autoriteit (NVWA)	Policy	Netherlands
11	ClearDetections B.V. (CD)	SME	Netherlands
12	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)	Research	Netherlands
13	International Plant Analysis & Diagnostics (IPADLAB)	SME	Italy
14	Sediag S.A.S. (SEDIAG)	SME	France
15	Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria (CREA)	Research	Italy
16	Główny Inspektorat Ochrony Roslin i Nasiennictwa (GIORIN)	Research	Poland

1. Research institutions
2. Industries, including SMEs developing diagnostic tools
3. Policy makers and organisations producing policy recommendations

2. Objectives of the document

This document is intended to provide a guide to manage the different dissemination and training activities in order to engage the target audience and to gain international visibility. This is a “living document” which may be modified over the project lifetime according to the needs. In order to review the effectiveness of the VALITEST dissemination and training strategy and measure the extent to which it is meeting the defined objectives, the outcomes and impact of these activities will be evaluated and discussed throughout the project life at the Steering Committee meetings and the general project meetings. The conclusions will be included in the updated plan and ultimately in the final Plan for the use and dissemination of results (PDER) to be provided at month 36.

This document also includes plans for internal communication between project partners.

The Dissemination and Training plan will ensure that

- (i) the interest and expectations of the different audiences targeted by the project are identified more precisely,
- (ii) the dissemination objectives are defined and a set of messages to achieve an effective information delivery to the different audiences is prepared, and
- (iii) the best dissemination media and means to reach the different target audiences are defined.

The dissemination and training plan should help raise awareness on the project's objectives on a larger scale, make the VALITEST results widely accessible, and ensure understandable and effective knowledge transfer among the various actors involved.

2.1. Dissemination and training objectives set up in the VALITEST project

The objectives of VALITEST dissemination and training activities can be summarised as follows:

- Contributing to the wider harmonization of the validation process
- Sharing validation data generated during the project
- Raising awareness and capacity building among stakeholders
- Enhancing product development by the diagnostics industry
- Increasing the project visibility
- Contributing to promote EU research

2.2. Dissemination and training targets

The following stakeholders have been initially identified and will be addressed during the project:

- The **scientific community**: Acceptance of the solid scientific and technological foundations and innovative aspects of VALITEST by these groups is an essential step for the credibility of the project results and outputs (procedures and validated diagnostic products).
- **Plant pest diagnostic laboratories**: Dissemination activities directed to this group of stakeholders will include information on the validated tests, guidelines for validation and interlaboratory comparisons produced and information on potential optimization of proficiency assessment. Plant pest diagnostic laboratories will also have the opportunity to participate in test performance studies.
- **Policy and decision makers and governmental authorities**: Policies related to plant health are under development at National, European and International level. Therefore, dissemination to this target group is also essential, not only to disseminate the achievements of the VALITEST project to them, but also with the aim of encouraging feedback and inputs from this group into the activities.
- **Diagnostics industry**: While several of the major diagnostics players in Europe directly participate as project partners, other diagnostic companies should be involved in the project and accessibility of the project outputs to the whole diagnostic industry is also considered as key for the long-term success of the project.
- **Inspection services, NPPOs**: Dissemination activities directed to this group of stakeholders will include information on the validated tests and guidelines produced.
- **Farmers/growers, landowners, agricultural advisors, breeders**: An important part of the VALITEST dissemination activities aims at making VALITEST outputs known by these **potential customers** and **end-users**. Efficiently attracting their interest while promoting the benefits of the project outputs, is essential to achieve commercial success and to widen the business opportunities of the industrial partners involved in VALITEST.

- **Accreditation bodies:** The outputs of the project concerning horizontal assessment of laboratories' proficiency have to be acceptable for accreditation. They will therefore be developed in close collaboration with accreditation bodies. The different outputs of the project (validation data and guidelines) will be presented to accreditation bodies at European and national levels.

The VALITEST dissemination target groups, the key messages to deliver and the dissemination tools are presented in table 2.

Table 2 – VALITEST dissemination target groups, key messages and dissemination tools		
Target groups	Key messages	Main Dissemination tools
Consumers and Society (general public)	Project objectives and results, with a particular focus on pest impacts and benefits of the outcomes to plant health	Project website, brochure, leaflets, social media accounts, general press articles, etc.
Farmers/growers, landowners, agricultural advisors, breeders	Project objectives and results; practical solutions for pest detection (e.g. on-site tools) to support pest management; training on tests.	Project website, brochure, leaflets, social media accounts, general press articles, training toolkit, workshops
Inspection services and NPPOs Policy and decision makers	Project objectives and results; practical solutions for pest detection (e.g. on-site tools) to support pest management; training on tests. Guidelines (validation, proficiency evaluation)	Project website, brochure, leaflets, social media accounts, technical and scientific articles, training toolkit, invitation to workshops
Scientific community	Project outcomes, Knowledge of end-users' needs (Innovation-driven research)	Scientific papers, posters, conferences and workshops, training toolkit, targeted communication, invitation to project meetings and workshops
Industries	Project objectives and results; new tools and procedures for diagnostics validation; evaluation of consumer perception; acceptability of novel products; business plan to support product development	Project website, brochure, leaflets, technical articles, social media accounts, direct communication by project partners

3. Communication Tools

3.1. Project contact email

Contact@valitest.eu

This mail box has an alias redirecting the messages to the EPPO Staff and to ANSES coordination team and will be monitored on a daily basis.

3.2. Visual identity

The visual identity is the representing image of the project, both for its internal and external communication. The VALITEST logo was chosen by the project partners through an internal survey. The chosen logo is displayed here below:

The VALITEST logo must be used in all project documents.

3.3. Use of EU emblem and acknowledgement

Any dissemination of project results must include certain references and statements, in particular:

- display the **EU emblem**

and

- include the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 773139"

"The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, etc.] represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility; it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Research Executive Agency or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains."

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Since it is considered as the corporate identity of the VALITEST project, both logos will be present in all dissemination materials and media, including: letterheads, templates for deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, website, Twitter Account...

3.4. Templates

Based on the same colour palette, fonts and logo, a set of templates have been proposed by EPPO. The templates ensure that the VALITEST visual identity is consistent throughout the duration of the project. This set of templates includes:

- A template for project deliverables (Annex 1);
- A template for project PowerPoint presentations (Annex 2);
- A template for letterhead example of the invitation letter for TPS (Annex 3);
- A website (Annex 4)

3.5. The Website

3.5.1) External communication

The website (Annex 4) constitutes a key communication tool in order to increase the project visibility and to share knowledge and information about the project. It is the most important and immediate point of reference for all target audiences. The website was constructed and made available from July 2018 (M 3).

The VALITEST website Url is: <https://www.valitest.eu/>

It contains all relevant information about the project (project objectives, information regarding the work packages, the partners and the advisory board, news regarding Test performance studies, training and event announcements) as it progresses.

The design has a clear and accessible structure and an intuitive system of links in order to make the navigation simple and user-friendly.

The website also hosts: a reserved area dedicated to internal communication and a collaborative platform.

The social media buttons (Twitter and Flickr) have been inserted to guarantee constant connection with the VALITEST social media account.

The website will be regularly updated with all the news about the project, including its outcomes, events, interviews, official articles and publications.

3.5.2) Internal communication

Internal communication, which facilitates the flow of information among partners, is considered of crucial importance, since it allows the smooth realization of project activities, besides encouraging knowledge exchange and research initiatives.

The project website has an access point to a secure collaborative workspace where all project partners can easily share, archive and exchange scientific, administrative and financial information and foster their collaboration at all levels. A link has been provided to the EPPO Extranet work space to achieve this objective. A 'Team VALITEST' workspace has been created and all project partners have been granted access to it.

Specific teams have also been created for the VALITEST Steering Committee and for the Advisory board using the Extranet.

“Team VALITEST” extranet

“Team VALITEST - Steering Committee” extranet

“Team VALITEST - Advisory board” extranet

The structure of the Work Area has been refined with the Steering Committee workspace. Mailing lists specific to the different Work Packages have been established as required. Mailing lists are available on EPPO extranet in the excel file: Valitest_List_of_contacts_updated date. The following mailing lists have also been created:

- a list for the participants involved in administrative work/tasks (adm@valitest.eu);
- a list for the participants involved in technical work/tasks (wp_all@valitest.eu);
- a list for the advisory board members (ab@valitest.eu).

3.6. VALITEST social media HUB

A VALITEST twitter account will contain all the news about the project and its activities. The VALITEST social media accounts will be managed by EPPO which will monitor and reply to the user-generated contents.

3.7. Brochure and flyers

Based on the summary of the project, information materials (project fact-sheet, flyers, poster) have been developed with the different partners (Month 12) and are available on the extranet and on the website.

3.8. Digital research object portal

In the framework of the XF-ACTORS European project (main page shown below) an online publicly accessible portal was built and made available for consultation, use and re-use of digital objects generated during the project by the stakeholders and more generally by anyone interested. The use of a similar portal will be evaluated.

Digital Research Object Portal

4. Interaction with stakeholders

4.1. Mapping of stakeholders

In the first part of the project, mapping of stakeholders will be carried out.

Some stakeholders are already known to partners in the project e.g. current networks of partners, through the EPPO Networks (laboratories registered in the EPPO Database of Diagnostic Expertise and NPPOs).

Contacts of end-users, including farmers/growers, landowners, agricultural advisors, breeders associations will be gathered in WP4 in strict compliance with GDPR. Initial contact is expected to be made through farmers / breeders associations. For an exemplary, non-exhaustive list please see Table 3.

Table 3 Non-exhaustive list of end-users, including farmers/growers, landowners, agricultural advisors, breeders associations

Country	Organisation	Website
International	International Plant Propagators' Society	http://www.ipps.org/
UK	Soil Association	https://www.soilassociation.org/
UK	Commercial Horticultural Association	http://www.cha-hort.com/index.htm
UK	Horticultural Trades Association	www.the-hta.org.uk
UK	National Farmers Union	https://www.nfuonline.com/home/
UK	Potato Council	https://potatoes.ahdb.org.uk/
Germany	Deutscher Bauernverband (farmers union)	https://www.bauernverband.de/information-english

Switzerland	Schweizer Bauernverband (farmers union)	https://www.sbv-usp.ch/en/
France	FNSEA (syndicate of farmers unions)	http://www.fnsea.fr/

Diagnostics industries have already been identified and contact persons will be identified in the first months of the project. A non-exhaustive list of European providers of tests for plant health diagnostics is presented in Table 4. This list should be completed by partners in Month 5 of the project.

Table 4 – Non-exhaustive list of European providers of tests for plant health diagnostics

Company	Country	Website
Agdia Biofords	France	http://www.agdia-biofords.com/
Agritest	Italy	http://www.agritest.it/
Bioreba	Switzerland	http://www.bioreba.ch/
ClearDetections	The Netherlands	http://www.cleardetections.com/
DSMZ	Germany	https://www.dsmz.de/
Enbiotech	Italy	http://enbiotech.eu/en/
Hyris	United Kingdom	http://www.hyris.net/
IPADLAB	Italy	http://ipadlab.eu/index.php/en
Loewe	Germany	http://www.loewe-info.com/
Optigene	United Kingdom	http://www.optigene.co.uk/
Plant Print Diagnostics	Spain	http://plantprint.net/
Pocket Diagnostics	United Kingdom	https://www.pocketdiagnostic.com/
Prime Diagnostics	The Netherlands	http://www.primediagnosics.com
Qualiplante	France	http://www.qualiplante.eu/
Sediag	France	http://www.sediag.com

For a continuous production of validation data for plant health diagnostic tests, which are relevant according to the needs of stakeholders, **appropriate dialogue tools should be developed**. Among others, **VALITEST will include the establishment of dedicated initiatives for the Plant Health Diagnostics Industry**, which are currently missing. It will provide:

- Better cooperation between kits suppliers to enhance their international competitiveness.
- An identified partner for discussion (e.g. in the framework of the development of new legislation, standard setting...).

4.2. Gathering of Stakeholders needs in diagnostics

Target needs and main interests will be identified through specific activities:

- Online surveys in order to precisely understand the needs of the stakeholders.
- Online survey to identify existing tests with validation data.
- Call for interest for diagnostic kits.
- Call for participants in the test performance studies (TPS).

Results from an initial survey with diagnostic laboratories are expected to highlight focus areas for which stakeholder feedback will need to be gathered.- **Targeted interviews** and surveys will then be used to compile and assess end-users areas of interest. Interview outputs will be worked into impact and market assessments.

5. Dissemination activities

Dissemination procedures: All dissemination activities must be approved by the consortium according to the provisions set in the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Grant Agreement (GA).

Tracking and reporting of Dissemination activities: Each partner should disseminate results, taking into account the confidentiality agreements set in the GA and CA. Dissemination through participation in events is described in point 5.1 of this document and dissemination through publication in point 5.2.

5.1. Dissemination through participation in events

5.1.1. Project events: Training Workshops

Several dissemination/training workshops for diagnostics laboratories were planned to be organised at two different levels to minimise travel costs:

- A large training event at the end of the project at EU level.
- At least 3 European and regional workshops gathering VALITEST end-users from different sectors and countries will be organised towards the end of the project, one for Eastern/Central Europe Organized in Poland (Glorin), one in Italy organized by CREA & NIB, one in the Netherlands organized by WR & Fera.

However, due to the Covid-19 pandemics, it was decided to organize all the training activities online. The following on-line activities will be organized in the first semester of 2021:

- Three webinar series (500 possible participants)
 - o One on the concept of validation
 - o One on the organization of TPS (including the analysis of the results)
 - o One on the use and validation of HTS tests
- Online practical training sessions (for a restricted number of participants)
 - o Analysis of the performance characteristics of a test
 - o Training and demonstration on the use of commercial kits
 - o How to organize a TPS?
 - o How to analyze the results of a TPS?
 - o How to use and validate a HTS test in my laboratory?

These activities will be organized by WP6 in collaboration with partners from different work packages that expressed their interest in participating to these events.

Webinars and video tutorials will be made available on the project website. New validation data generated, or existing validation data gathered during the project will be made available through an improved version of the EPPO Database on diagnostics expertise (section validation data).

5.1.2. Project events: meetings with policy makers

Meetings will be organised with European policy-makers to exchange information about validated tests, and about the project. The first meetings will be mainly used to seek concrete feedback from policy makers in order to better shape the work. The last meetings will allow the consortium to inform the policy makers of project outputs and provide useful information to shape policies. Engagement with policy makers will also involve invitation of the EC officers (from DGs RTD and SANCO) to the project meetings.

Dissemination activities will also take place in the framework of the International Year of Plant Health IYPH2020 and through other meetings organized in the EPPO region at this occasion.

5.1.3. Participation in external events

Project results will be presented in scientific conferences selected for their excellence and attendance of key actors and decision makers (e.g. International Symposium on Crop Protection in Ghent, International Congress of Plant Pathology (ICPP) 2018 in Boston (US), International Plant Protection Congress 2019 in India, EPPO Panels on diagnostics).

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results through participation in events must give an advance notice to the other beneficiaries of at least 20 days before registration submission, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

This notice should be done through an email sent to all partners (e.g. participants involved in the technical aspect of the project) using the wp_all@valitest.eu mailing list explaining the objective and the content of the dissemination and, if relevant, through the upload on the extranet of the abstract of the communication that will be done. A notice is not required when only general information regarding the project (for example objectives, general description of the workpackages...) are communicated.

Any other beneficiary may object within 10 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

When the project participants will actively attend external events (such as conferences, exhibitions, workshops) on behalf of the project, their presence will be highlighted and communicated mainly through the social media platform of the project. This activity will raise the visibility of the project and will show and enhance the scientific exchange between researchers.

5.1.4. Reporting dissemination actions during external events

A template for reporting of dissemination actions is presented in Annex 5.

Further templates on the evaluation of the project outcome will be developed as necessary during the project (specific training evaluation forms, review of stakeholder's engagement).

5.2. Dissemination via publications

At least 5 joint papers will be submitted to international journals by the end of the project (e.g. European Journal of Plant Pathology, EPPO Bulletin, Euroreference, Accreditation and quality assurance journal...). A book with provisional title *Critical points of test performance study organization in microbiology, case study: Plant pests* will be published in Plant Pathology in the 21st Century Springer Book series.

At least 10 articles will be submitted to the specialized press in national languages by the end of the project.

According to Horizon 2020 legal requirement, open access to all scientific publications relating to project results will be ensured (at least "green" open access/self-archiving, "gold open access as far as possible). (All partners).

VALITEST partners will publish the results they consider relevant (according to the IPR protection strategy and to the GA and the CA) in scientific journals and magazines. Results will be also published on the VALITEST website and newsletter.

Publications must follow the following provisions according to the statements included in the CA and GA:

- Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other partners at least **45 calendar days** before the publication (Art 29.1 of the GA).

- Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within **30 calendar days** after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted (Art 29.1 of the GA).
- Any **objection** is justified if the partner can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests (Art 29.1 of the GA).

If an objection is raised, it has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

If an objection has been raised, the involved parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.

Each party **must ensure open access** (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results (see 4.8. Digital research object portal).

Moreover, the partner must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

Each partner shall:

- ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest: on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication in any other case.
- ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

Grant Agreement number:

773139 — VALITEST

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

5.3. Specific procedure regarding the dissemination of validation data generated by WP1

In addition to the procedures described in 5.1 and 5.2, the following strategy has been agreed by the partners regarding the dissemination of the Test Performance Studies (TPS) results obtained within the framework of WP1.

- By default, the name of all the tests selected for the TPS and the associated validation data can be used for dissemination activities.
- However, before any dissemination of TPS results including tests using commercial kits, teleconferences will be organized by WP1. The relevant commercial partners from WP7 are invited to these meetings so they can discuss the results of the TPS with the TPS organizers. During these meetings, they can oppose the dissemination of the name of their kits and/or of the associated validation data. Summary reports of the TPS results (e.g. power point presentations) will be sent to the commercial partners at least 2 weeks before these meetings.

6. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The success of the dissemination strategy will be implemented and monitored closely throughout the project.

Appropriate web analytics software has been installed on the project website to enable closer inspection of web traffic (including numbers of tweets, retweets and likes), including investigating any observed changes in traffic surrounding key project events, as well as basic information about visitors and the use they make of the site.

The results of this monitoring process will be reviewed at the regular consortium management meetings. Such discussions will provide an opportunity to identify particular gaps or overlaps in existing dissemination activities and adjust the strategic direction accordingly during the project itself.

7. Roles and responsibilities of partners

Partners shall make all efforts to timely communicate to EPP0 any useful update and information related to the project achievements, in order to allow effective and timely communication and dissemination actions.

8. List of Annex

Annex 1: Deliverable template

Annex 2: PowerPoint presentation template

Annex 3: A template for letterhead: example of the invitation letter for TPS (Annex 3);

Annex 4: Template of the VALITEST website

Annex 5: Template for reporting of dissemination actions

ANNEX 1- Deliverable template

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 773139

Grant agreement N. 773139

DELIVERABLE N°

Title:

Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health

Due date:	
Actual submission data	
Start date of the project	01-05-2018
Deliverable lead contractor (organization name)	
Participants (Partners short names)	
Author(s) in alphabetical order	
Contact for queries	
Level of dissemination	
Deliverable status	

Abstract:
Partners involved Task X, Y

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3.1 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 14, Bold)	4
3.1.1 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 12, Bold)	4
3.2 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 12, Bold)	4
4 Conclusion and recommendations	4
REFERENCES	4
ANNEX	4

The content highlighted in yellow can be modified considering the type of the Deliverable

TERMS, ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

If necessary

1 Purpose

The aim of this deliverable is to ...

2 Scope

This deliverable is applicable to ...

3 Methodology (TITLE FONT: CALIBRI, 14, BOLD)

3.1 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 14, Bold)

3.1.1 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 12, Bold)

Xxx... (Text Font: Calibri, 11)

3.2 XXX... (Title Font: Calibri, 12, Bold)

Xxx... (Text Font: Calibri, 11)

4 Conclusion and recommendations

REFERENCES

If necessary

[1] xxx

[2] xxx

ANNEX

If necessary

Please use Footnotes. Footnotes Font: Calibri, 9

Cliquez pour ajouter un
titre

Cliquez pour ajouter un sous-titre

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 773139 as requested by the GA, art. 29.4.

Cliquez pour ajouter un titre

- Cliquez pour ajouter du texte

ANNEX 3 - A template for letterhead: example of the invitation letter for TPS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 773139

To whom it may concern

[Day, XX Month, Year]

TPS organizer:
[Institution]

Subject: VALITEST H2020 –Test Performance Study Organization
Encl.: TPS Interest - Information Form

Pest name:
[pest]

Dear Sir or Madam,

We are contacting you in the framework of an EU funded research project, VALITEST (<https://www.valitest.eu>), which aims to improve plant pests diagnostics. Validation is essential to provide information on the performance of the tests that are used in diagnostic. However, most detection and identification tests are currently only validated on an intra-laboratory basis or through limited test performance studies (TPS), and there is a need to further harmonize practices.

Followed by:
[TPS coordinator]

By this message, we are seeking your interest to take part to a test performance study. Indeed, you have been identified as a potential participant for a TPS for the detection of [pest].

Telephone number:
[number]

The expected timeline is as follows:

Period of TPS: [date] - [date]
Sending of the samples: [date] - [date]
Deadline for performing analysis: [date]
Deadline for participants reporting of on the results: [date]

E- mail:
[email]

In the table below you can find the methods to be evaluated together with the scope of TPS for [pest]:

Method			
Sample type			
Matrix			
Suitable for			
Purpose			
Type of controls needed			
No. of samples			
Maximum no. of tests to be evaluated ¹			

¹Please note that the number of methods and tests is indicative at this step. It will be adjusted according to the results of preliminary tests and participation interest.

[Institute, address]
[phone number]
[email]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 773139

If you are not a VALITEST project partner and as the project's budget does not allow any external funding, the participation to the TPS will be at your own cost (consumables, chemicals, reagents). If you are a VALITEST project partner, you already benefit from a dedicated budget for participation to the TPS.

As a participant to the TPS, you would receive the evaluation report and you would be associated to the results exploitation. The samples are expected to include **[DNA, RNA, deactivated plant extracts and/or viable pest]**.

Participants will be selected based on pre-defined criteria. In order to optimize our organization and the reliability of the TPS, we would like to get some practical details concerning your organization.

To express your interest in participating, please, fill in the enclosed excel file named 'TPS Interest - Information Form' and return it in digital form by e-mail to **[email]** by **[date]**. We will inform you about your possibility to participate by **[date]**. There are critical selection criteria, which need to be fulfilled for participation in TPS:

- Time schedule described above compatible with your availability
- Authorization by the national competent authority to work with the specific pest (**[viable pest/ inactivated pest/ DNA/ RNA]** will be shipped)
- Traceability in place / QA in place
- Possibility to obtain an import document or Letter of Authority (EU countries)

Candidates which are able and committed to perform all methods will have an advantage in TPS selection process, **whereas it is necessary to perform all tests for the selected method**. If more than the maximum number of laboratories fulfill all selection criteria for a specific test, participants are selected on "first come, first served" basis.

In the frame of the same project TPS for 6 different pathogens altogether will be organized: Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus, *Xylophilus ampelinus*, *Xanthomonas citri* **pv.** *citri*, Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus, *Cryphonectria parasitica*, Plum Pox Virus, therefore, you might have/will receive additional invitation letters for the listed pathogens during September 2019.

Please do not hesitate to contact us should you require additional information.

Yours sincerely,

[TPS coordinator]
TPS coordinator

[Institute, address]
[www] [email]
[phone]

Welcome to VALITEST

2018-05 to 2021-04

Introduction and context

Global food security is the most significant challenge mankind is facing in the 21st century due to the 'perfect storm' of a growing population (estimated to exceed 9 billion by 2050), climate change, demand for energy, increased pressure on natural resources, slowing of agricultural productivity growth and decline in the land area under agriculture. Additionally, although it is estimated that a 50% increase in food production will be needed by 2050, currently a quarter of the world's crops are lost to pests, causing major economic losses and social impacts globally. Protecting crops against these losses from farm to fork is critical for achieving sustainable and competitive agriculture as well as for the protection of biodiversity and ecosystems. Establishing smart surveillance mechanisms is essential to the fulfilment of this important goal, as these enable effective monitoring and control of introduction and spread of plant pest.

Early diagnosis and a rapid response are crucial to reduce the risk of entry and spread of plant pests and ultimately their impacts. Furthermore, it is recognized that plant pests can be managed most effectively when control measures are implemented at an early stage of infestation. National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) routinely perform pest diagnosis as part of export certification, import inspections, pest surveillance and eradication programs. In 2016, the Commission on Phytosanitary Measures adopted a recommendation on diagnostics recognizing that 'pest diagnosis is a cross-cutting issue that underpins most International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) activities. In order to take action against a pest, it must be accurately identified. To enable safe trade, pest diagnosis must further be completed quickly and to a high level of confidence.'

Validation is essential to provide information on the performance of the tests that are used in diagnostic. However, most detection and identification tests are currently only validated on an intra-laboratory basis or through limited test performance studies (TPS), and there is a need to further harmonize practices.

Why companies should be interested?

- VALITEST aims to bring onto the market **tests validated** according to international standards and produced by small and medium size **companies manufacturing diagnostic kits. Even if you are not a partner** there will be opportunities for you to have your kits evaluated during the tests performance studies organized in WP1.
- VALITEST aims to establish an **EU association of the Plant Health Diagnostic Industry**
- VALITEST aims to develop an **EU Plant Health Diagnostic Charter**.

Read more in WP7, and identify partners involved in the project.

Twitter

Work Packages and deliverables

Quick links

- WP 1: VALIDATION OF TESTS FOR IDENTIFIED NEEDS AND SPECIFIC PESTS
- WP 2: IMPROVEMENT OF THE VALIDATION PROCESS
- WP 3: QUALITY ASSURANCE FOR REFERENCE MATERIALS FOR VALIDATION PURPOSES
- WP 4: ANALYSIS OF DEMAND FOR TESTING AND IMPACTS
- WP 5: OPTIMISATION OF PROFICIENCY EVALUATION FOR A HORIZONTAL ASSESSMENT
- WP 6: DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND TRAINING
- WP 7: MARKET EXPLOITATION OF THE PROJECT RESULTS
- WP 8: MANAGEMENT OF THE CONSORTIUM AND THE PROJECT
- WP 9: ETHICS REQUIREMENTS

Follow Us On

Work Package 1

Validation of tests for identified needs and specific pests
 WP Leaders : Dr. Marcel Westenberg and Dr Maja Ravnikar (until M13)
 WP Leaders : Dr Maja Ravnikar and Dr Géraldine ANTHOINE (from M14)

WP1 focus on validation of tests using different methods (i.e. (real-time) PCR, LAMP, ELISA, LFD) according to EPPO Standard PM 7/098, but improved especially by including a statistical approach developed in the framework of WP2.

Performance criteria of several tests will be determined by organizing interlaboratory test performance studies (TPS) according to EPPO Standard PM 7/122, in which participating laboratories will use the same test for analysing identical sets of reference samples simulating the samples routinely analysed.

Two rounds of tests performance studies will be organised.

- The first round will be organized in early 2019 for six prioritized pests (*Erwinia amylovora*, *Pantoea stewartii*, *citrus tristeza virus*, *plum pox virus*, *Fusarium circinatum* and *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) in a range of matrices and for a range of methods.
- The second round will be performed in 2020 on pests and associated tests based on the needs of stakeholders and to the market analysed in the framework of WP4.

Erwinia amylovora

List of deliverables for WP1

- 1.1. Report detailing the minimum performance parameters to select tests for validation and selection of laboratories for TPS
- 1.2. List of tests for validation - Round 1
- 1.3. List of tests for validation - Round 2

Partners

All Research institution SME Intergovernmental Organisation Industry NPPO

ANSES
French agency for food, environmental and occupational health & safety
Investigate, evaluate, protect

French agency for food, environmental and occupational health & safety

AGRINNOVA
University of Turin

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation
Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER
Agroscope

LOEWE
Loewe Biochemica GmbH

BIOREBA
Your Partner in Agro-Diagnostics

Bioreba AG

Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER - Agroscope

NIB
NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF BIOLOGY

fera
Original thinking... applied

Fera Science Ltd.

European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization

Training & Events

Archives

- > [Spring 2020](#)
- > [October 2019](#)
- > [September 2019](#)
- > [February 2019](#)
- > [May 2018](#)

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All TRAINING EVENTS TEST PERFORMANCE STUDIES

2020 SPRING **Second round of test performance studies (TPS) – start date**

The second round of TPS will start in spring 2020. If you are interested in participating to one or several TPS, please send us an email to contact@valitest.eu by **mid-October 2019 at the latest**.

IMPORTANT: If you are not a VALITEST project partner and as the project's budget does not allow any external funding, the participation to the TPS will be at your own cost. As a participant to the TPS, you would receive the evaluation report and you would be associated to the results exploitation.

2019 OCTOBER 1-2 **VALITEST mid-term conference**

The VALITEST mid-term conference will be held at the **Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification (CREA-DC)** in Rome on the 1st and 2nd of October 2019.

2019 SEPTEMBER **Second round of test performance studies (TPS) – Pests selection**

The preparation of the second round of Test performance studies (TPS) has started. Six pests (3 virus, 2 bacteria, 1 fungi) have been selected thanks to the collaborative work of the people from WP1 and WP4. The organizers (ANSES, CREA, FERA, NIB, UNITO) of each TPS has been identified. The selection of the tests that will be part of each TPS is ongoing.

Publications

Quick links

[FLYER](#) [POSTER](#) [FACTSHEET](#)

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Dissemination, communication and training

Work Package 6
WP Leader : Mrs Françoise PETTER

Valitest Flyer

Valitest - a multi-actor project

Objectives of the project

- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.
- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.
- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.

List of Partners

Valitest - a multi-actor project

Valitest Poster

Valitest - a project to improve the validation framework in the EU for plant pest diagnostics

Objectives of the project

- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.
- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.
- To provide high quality and state-of-the-art diagnostic services to plant health professionals in the EU for plant pest diagnostics.

A multi-actor project

Valitest - a multi-actor project

ANNEX 5 - Template for reporting of dissemination actions

The following table has to be completed by each partner for each official VALITEST **project dissemination event**.

<i>Title or name of the event</i>				<input type="checkbox"/> Organized by third parties	Date:	<i>specify</i>
				<input type="checkbox"/> Organized by VALITEST partners	Location:	<i>specify</i>
Type of event	<input type="checkbox"/> Conference	<input type="checkbox"/> seminar	<input type="checkbox"/> Workshop	<input type="checkbox"/> Exhibition	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<i>specify</i>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Show case/demo	<input type="checkbox"/> meeting	<input type="checkbox"/> forum	<input type="checkbox"/> visit		
Description	<i>Main focus, organizers, topics addressed, periodicity</i>				Associated costs	<i>specify</i>
VALITEST contribution	<i>Presentation subject or name of the lecture, purpose of VALITEST presentation, partners involved</i>				Responsible partners	<i>specify</i>
Audience	<input type="checkbox"/> Research/academics	<input type="checkbox"/> Industry	<input type="checkbox"/> Growers	<input type="checkbox"/> Policy makers/authorities	<input type="checkbox"/> other	<i>specify</i>
				Number of attendants		<i>specify</i>
Feedback	<i>Short summary of the event</i>					
Material	<i>PowerPoint presentations, posters leaflets, video...</i>					

Regarding participation in all other external events, the partners are invited to send a brief summary to EPPO who will publish it in the news section on the VALITEST website.